

Some Thoughts on the Mechanism of Biochemical Reproduction Reactions and Drug Actions

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The mechanism of nature's most baffling process of biochemical reproduction reactions, has been discussed on the consideration of a new type of electrometric-inductive resonance process postulated to operate simultaneously in a group of at least three structurally related molecules. A quantitative expression in the form of a 'geometrical progression relationship', has been proposed for the growth rate of reproduction of biological species. Various other factors which may influence the kinetics of reproduction reactions have also been discussed.

Proposed mechanism throws considerable light on the drug action of chemotherapeutic substances, which are structurally related to essential metabolites and thus it can help in the exploration of new drugs for certain unconquered diseases like cancer etc.

THE concept of electron transfer processes in biological systems was advanced by Szent-Gyorgyi¹ in 1941. He postulated that the π electrons in excited organic molecules, consisting of conjugated double bonds, might possess the characteristics of "free" electrons analogous to those present in metals and semiconductors; the excited molecules in biological systems rise to common energy levels or continuum, along which energy namely, electrons can travel a considerable distance; the motion of electrons is associated with the semiconductors in living systems.

Eley^{2,3} and others advanced "Band Model" and "Tunnel Model" for semiconduction properties of organic compounds. Since Szent-Gyorgyi hypothesis, many biochemical problems were considered to be basically the problems of charge or energy transfer over appreciably long distances through rather weakly linked but highly organised systems⁴ and various biological processes were attributed to the phenomenon of charge transfer⁵⁻¹⁰. Functional properties of a large number of biological systems were explained through the mechanism of charge transfer along the equal energy level within molecules^{7,10}.

Brillonj^{10,11} proposed that the periodic structure of DNA molecule should give rise to energy bands within the molecules and the donor-acceptor systems should be formed by the energy of bases. Electron transfer from protein to hydrocarbon was attributed as an important step in carcinogenesis¹². Pullmann¹³ gave a quantitative basis for the formation of other charge transfer complexes - the compounds, formed from the interaction of a variety of molecules - primarily aromatics which can behave as electron donor (D), with electron acceptors (A) of various structures.

The basic concept of Szent-Gyorgyi of electron transfer through excited energy level continua and subsequent studies of the behaviour of electron transfer complexes, have provided insight to the

mechanism of certain bimolecular interaction processes which occur owing to the presence of charge donor and acceptor groups in the same or two different molecules. Yet these developments have not thrown any light on the most baffling phenomena of nature, namely, bio-chemical reproduction reactions.

In the present paper, the author is proposing a mechanism for these most complicated processes by considering them as 'trimolecular or multimolecular interaction systems of biochemistry'.

The biochemical reactions can be distinguished from the other types of chemical reactions in (a) their "reproduction" behaviour, and (b) in the physiological activity of the substances structurally related to essential metabolites. A biochemical species multiplies itself in its own culture. This reproduction feature is responsible for the growth of entire animal and plant kingdom. The mechanism of biochemical reproduction reactions has been explained here on the considerations of a new type of inductive resonance process postulated to operate simultaneously in a group of at least three structurally related molecules. A quantitative expression in the form of a geometrical progression law has been obtained for the growth rate of reproduction of biological species.

The investigations on the biochemical action of several families of synthetic drugs, vitamins and enzymes on substrates have given support to Fildes hypothesis¹⁴ that synthetic substances which are structurally related to essential metabolites destroy the organism by a competitive antagonism of the chemical function of the essential metabolite. However, the mechanism operative in "reproduction reactions", in the competitive growth of virus and bacteria, in the context of a relationship between the structures of enzymes and drugs and their biochemical activities, is not well understood. The metabolic processes which are very specific, differ from other thermodynamic reactions and surface

processes in their low energies of activation and the structural resemblance of the active material with the substrate.

Postulations of the mechanism: The important concepts involved in the theory presented here are as follows:

1. The processes of transfer of electrons to long distances along the chain of atoms in saturated and unsaturated-conjugate bonded systems of organic molecules occur either due to inductometric effect or mesomeric (electrometric) effect or due to the absorption of external energy of a photon.

2. All the above three effects are complimentary and not contradictory to one another and they can occur individually or collectively in biochemical phenomena of nature; further, any one or more of these effects can be responsible for a number of biochemical phenomena and physico-chemical properties of organic systems.

3. The long chains of atoms along which electrons travel, may constitute common energy level continua in molecules and the mobile electrons may behave as free electrons, analogous to those considered to be present in a metal or a semiconductor, and can give rise to semiconduction and other similar properties in organic systems.

4. Accumulation or depletion of these free electrons at certain atoms or groups in a compound may result in the polarisation of the molecules.

5. The molecules under the influence of inductometric effect, electrometric effect and absorption of external energy, may undergo a permanent, periodic or temporary polarisation cum activation respectively and during which period they would be prone to chemical transformation.

6. Since electrons can travel along a chain of atoms in their normal state under electrometric effect, many of the biochemical transformations including reproduction reactions are the consequences of mesomerism, superimposed with inductometric effect of electrophilic and nucleophilic groups of atoms present in organic systems.

7. Reproduction reactions in biochemical systems and drug actions in biological metabolism may involve a trimolecular (or multi-molecular) interaction among structurally related molecules.

8. When a minimum of three such structurally related molecules come in close vicinity of one another, they form a trimolecular hybrid system designated here as "breathing molecule". This pseudo molecule may undergo mesomeric-inductive-resonance, resulting in the transfer of charges, activation of electrophilic or nucleophilic groups in the two molecules adjacent to the central bridge molecule and finally in the chemical transformation of the adjacent molecules to produce a product identical to the bridge molecule of the pseudo chain of the triplet system.

9. These reproduction reactions may not need any external energy for the excitation of electrons of donor and acceptor groups in the trimolecular

hybrid system and hence these reactions may occur at the normal energy state of molecules.

The theory: The reactivity of electrometric and nucleophilic groups in organic compounds, which consist of multi conjugated bonds, is largely controlled by the electrometric relay of electric charges from atom to atom down the chain. Such a phenomenon of transmission of electrons within the structures of organic molecules can occur either as a result of elevation of the molecule to a higher energy band through the absorption of external energy of a photon, as conceived by Szent-Gyorgyi¹, or as a result of the transmission of electrons through a molecule in normal state due to mesomerism — the conjugative mechanism of electron displacement. Once a molecule is under mesomeric effect or is excited to higher energy band, the band electrons in either case attains the freedom similar to that of free electrons in metals or semiconductors. These mobile electrons enhance the reactivity of electrometric or nucleophilic groups or say the donor or acceptor capabilities of the groups attached to a molecule. The phenomenon of transmission of electric influence has been discussed in literature with reference to two molecule systems in which one molecule is subjected to the influence of external field of a second polarised molecule through the empty space, instead of through a chain of linkages.

The author postulates that such a phenomenon of mesomerism leading to the electrometric relay of electronic charges through the conjugated bonds and hence to the polarisation of molecules may not be confined to a system consisting of two molecules only wherein the substituent groups of one confers the field effect upon the other. The phenomenon can occur simultaneously in a bunch of a larger number of structurally related molecules as and when they happen to come in close proximity of one another and orient in suitable positions without linking to one another.

Let us consider a molecule of Y—R—Y type which resonates owing to the presence of a pair of conjugate bonds, as schematically indicated in equation 1.

In this process of resonance, a quantum of charge of say δe magnitude rolls in to and fro directions in between carbon atoms 1 and 4 rendering them alternately positive and negative. The resonance brings down the energy of the system and thus keeps Y_1 and Y_2 firmly bound to the benzene nucleus.

Let us consider a reaction system schematically represented in equation 2, where a compound A—R—B of intermediate configuration is present in close proximity and in a suitably oriented position in between the other two molecules

A—R—A and B—R—B of extreme configurations, R being an aromatic or conjugated aliphatic structure and A and B are the substituent electron repellent and electron sink groups respectively. The molecule I possesses only a pair of electron repellent, while the molecule III a pair of electron sink groups. The numbers suffixed to A and B groups represent their respective positions in the hybridised structure.

The field effect of groups A_3 and B_3 would impart electrometric influence on the adjacent molecules I and III and disturb their resonance hybrid represented by eq. 1; hence an additional electronic charge of magnitude δe_1 will be drifted in direction of groups A_3 to A_1 in molecule I under the influence of the electron repellent force of the groups A_3 on A_2 ; while a charge of magnitude say δe_2 would be drifted in the molecule III in the direction B_1 to B_2 owing to the electrophilic nature of the group B_3 . The electron charge drift in the two molecules, I and III, would thus be complementary in nature with regard to the direction. Subsequently owing to the symmetrical positions of A_1 and A_3 in relation to A_2 and of B_1 and B_3 in relation to B_2 , the charge inertia δe_1 and δe_2 will recoil in molecules I and III in the directions A_1 to A_2 and B_1 to B_2 respectively and $(\delta e_1 - \delta e_2)$ in the direction of A_3 to B_3 in the molecule II, bringing the molecules I and III again to their normal states from the activated state.

Thus, under this state, a certain unit of charge relays continuously in to and fro directions in between two "A" groups attached to I and the momentum of the charge inertia is synchronically communicated to the molecule III via molecule II. The transmission of the momentum of the charge inertia between the molecules I and III does not impart any strain on the intermediate molecule as the total charge drift through II is only $(\delta e_1 - \delta e_2)$ which is very small in comparison to δe_1 or δe_2 . The bridge molecule merely forms a pseudo-chain and thus helps to reduce the activation energy of interactions between I and III, by providing a resonance tunnel through which the electronic charge can roll from one end of the chain to the other.

This hybridised system consisting of three molecules may be designated as a "breathing molecule" and the phenomenon occurring here as "inductive resonance".

In this process of charge relay across the tri-molecular pseudo-chain, the extreme groups A_1 and B_1 are raised to highly activated stage leading to the accumulation of negative charge at group A_1 and simultaneously recedes from electrophilic group

B_1 weakening the bond strength between these groups and the benzene nuclei. At this crucial moment of excitation, the molecules I and III are rendered highly placable to chemical transformations such as mutual exchange of the electrophilic groups B_1 and nucleophilic groups A_1 , hydrolysis of the molecules, etc. The exchange of A_1 and B_1 groups then result in the formation of three molecules of

identical structure $A \text{---} \text{---} B$ in the presence of a

single molecule of the same configuration. This is the phenomenon of "reproduction" which occurs so widely in the animal and plant kingdom. By this mechanism, a molecular species, in presence of structurally related substrates, multiplies itself from 1 to 3 and then to 9 to 27 and so on following the geometrical progression expression 3^n where n represents a particular step in the multiplication process. 'Growth rate factor' of a species can be quantitatively represented by the equation :

$$K = (3X)^{T/t} \quad \dots (3)$$

where $T/t = n$, T being the reaction time (in seconds), t the time (in seconds) taken for the completion of one stage of the growth reaction or say $1/t$ the frequency of multiplication reactions, and X the number of the molecules of the species present at the time $T=0$ which undergoes multiplication. The investigation of Hinshelwood and coworkers¹⁶ on the kinetics of the growth of certain bacteria, supports the above conclusion that the reproduction processes follow a geometrical progression law.

Let us consider an arbitrary example where

X = 1 molecule of a bacterial species

t = $\frac{1}{3}$ minute

T = 1 to 60 minutes

Substituting these values in equation 3, we get the values of K which are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—REPRODUCTION RATE OF BIOCHEMICAL SPECIES WITHIN 60 MINUTES

Time (T) in minutes	Reproduction number
1	3
2	9
3	27
4	81
5	243
6	729
7	2187
8	6561
9	19683
10	59049
15	1.44×10^7
20	3.49×10^8
25	8.47×10^{11}
30	2.06×10^{14}
35	5.00×10^{16}
40	1.22×10^{19}
45	2.95×10^{21}
50	7.18×10^{23}
55	1.74×10^{26}
60	4.24×10^{28}

It may be noted from the Table that a species of as large as $\frac{1}{3}$ minute reaction time, grows to 3

numbers in one minute and billions and billions numbers within 60 min. The growth rate can further increase with the decrease of t and further increase with the increase of T . Because of the low values of this factor, t , the virus and bacteria of some of the infectious diseases grow and spread fast. The larger the factor t of a species, the sluggish will be its growth rate.

Special features of the reaction mechanism : It may be noted that these reproduction reactions are initiated only by the product of its reaction. Growth process of these reactions is, therefore, highly specific and a definite species alone can multiply in a particular metabolic environment owing to the dependency of the biological activity upon the chemical constitution of the active materials. The reproduction reactions are irreversible processes as they do not constitute a thermodynamic equilibrium between the reactants and the product.

Factors influencing the kinetics of growth reactions : The kinetics of a reproduction reaction would depend upon the magnitude of the momentum of charge inertia operative in the whole system. If

$$(\delta e_1 \sim \delta e_2) \gg 0 \quad \dots (4)$$

the system would be sluggish. On the other hand, if

$$(\delta e_1 \sim \delta e_2) = 0 \text{ or very small} \quad \dots (5)$$

the trimolecular pseudo-chain would behave as a perfect resonating system wherein the charge pulses would readily be communicated from the molecule I to III and vice versa without straining the molecule II to the least.

The length of R would not impart any steric hindrance to the electrometric relay of charge, provided the conditions of eq. 5 is satisfied. However, the magnitude of T may get altered to some degree with the change in the length of R.

The nature and the positions of the substituent groups would offer the steric hindrance to the relay of the charge and hence would influence the magnitude of charge inertia as expressed by equation 4. A slight change in the nature of the substituent groups or in the structure of the bridging or side arms of the molecules would profoundly influence the degree of activation of the trimolecular pseudo chain systems and the speed of the reaction ; a growth reaction may become sluggish or be completely arrested under such a change.

Among the physical factors, light, electrical and magnetic fields and nuclear radiations would influence the speed and the nature of these reproduction reactions to a significant extent.

Bacteriostatic action of drugs : Consider a trimolecular system where the group B_a in the bridge molecule is replaced by another slightly stronger electron sink (acceptor) group B_a' . The new molecule A_a-R-B_a' by virtue of its stronger

groups will replace A-R-B from the breathing molecule and will not allow the formation of fresh trimolecular pseudo-chain system with A-R-B as the bridging molecules. This new trimolecular aggregate would not form a resonance hybrid owing to its asymmetrical structure and thus it would arrest the growth reaction viz., A-R-B multiplication or other types of biochemical processes. Fields' hypothesis of 'metabolic antagonism' as the basis of drug action is explicitly explained by the present theory. The bacteriostatic activity of the sulphonamide and other chemotherapeutic substances¹⁷ is due to their entrance into the reaction ring in competition with the metabolic substrate in an enzyme reaction and thus arresting the later. A chemotherapeutic substance acting as a drug may therefore be defined as "the substance which is structurally related to a metabolic substrate but which differs in one of the substituted groups and is thus capable of upsetting the resonance hybrid and arresting the growth of the virus or bacterial species which is responsible for a disease". Proposed mechanism of reproduction reactions occurring in biological systems, including bacterial and virus, opens new fields for the discovery of many new highly effective drugs for various hitherto unconquered diseases. A deep understanding of the chemistry of human system on the one hand and that of the plants and herbs on the other, in the light of the theory advanced in this paper, can help in the revelation of greater secrets of drug actions.

Explaining the mechanism of nature's most baffling process of biochemical reproduction reactions, the present theory concludes that the biochemical reactions are pure chemical processes independent of life. Life in biological organism¹⁸ may be a compendium of multitudes of well organised interlinked chemical processes while the soul imbedded in the life processes is something beyond the materialistic definition and it falls outside the scope of all physical sciences and so this paper.

References

1. A. SZENT-GYORGYI, *Nature*, 1941, 148, 157 ; 1946, 155, 875 ; *Diss. Faraday Soc.*, 1959, 27, 111.
2. D. D. ELEY, G. D. PARFITT, M. J. PARRY and D. H. TAYSUM, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, 49, 79.
3. D. D. ELEY and G. D. PARFITT, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, 51, 1529.
4. M. KASHA and B. PULLMAN, (Eds.), "Horizons in Biochemistry," Academic Press, New York, 1962 ; A. L. LEHNINGER, "Biochemistry", 2nd Ed., Worth Publishers, Inc., New York ; Kalyani Publishers, Ludhiana, 1979, p. 477, 587.
5. B. CHANCE and D. DAVAVULT, *Ber Bunsenges Phys. Chem.*, 1964, 68, 722 ; J. GERGELY, in H. KALLMANN, and M. SILVER, (Eds.), "Symposium on Electrical Conductivity in Organic Solids", Interscience, New York, 1961, p. 369.
6. D. NACHMANSOHN, "Chemical and Molecular Basis of Nerve Activity", Academic Press, New York, 1959.
7. H. MEIER, *Z. Wiss. Photo Photophysik. Photochem.*, 1953, 1 ; *Z. physik. Chem.*, 1958, 208, 340.
8. F. GUTMAN and L. E. LYONS, "Organic Semiconductors", John Wiley & Sons, Inc., N. Y., 1967.
9. M. CALVIN, *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1959, 31, 147.

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10. D. B. CLAYSON, "Chemical Carcinogeneses", Little Brown & Co., Boston, 1962., D. D. ELEY, *Discussion Faraday Soc.*, 1959, 27, 242.
11. L. BRILLONI, *Cancers Phys.*, 1961, 15, 413, also Ref. 4, p. 295.
12. E. J. AMBROSE and F. J. C. ROE, (Ed.) "The Biology of Cancer", Van Nostrand, London, 1966; D. R. WILLIAMS, *Chem. Reviews*, 1972, 72, 203.
13. A. PULLMAN and B. PULLMAN, *Advances in Cancer Research*, 1955, 3, 117.
14. FIELDS, *Lancet*, 1940, 955.
15. C. K. INGOLD, "Introduction to Structure in Organic Chemistry", G. Bell and Sons Ltd., London, 1956, p. 60.
16. C. L. HINSHELWOOD, *Biol. Rev.*, 1944, 19, 150; *Chem. Soc., Am., Rep.*, 1945, 15.
17. "The Chemical Kinetics of the Bacterial Cell", Oxford Univ. Press, 1946; W. A. Sexton, "Chemical Constitution and Biological Activity", E. and F. N. Son Ltd., London, p. 41.
18. A. L. LEHNINGER, "Biochemistry", 2nd Edn., Worth Publishers, Inc., New York; Kalyani Publishers, Ludhiana, 1979, p. 477, 587.